

Migration and Transformation: Understanding the Impact on Destination Countries in the Age of Mobility

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Abstract

The impacts of migration on both migrants and the places through which they move are often significant but rarely simple to elucidate. In many cases migration is associated with a series of costs and benefits, which are often very difficult to quantify or judge against one another. One of the reasons behind the migrant's movement from one nation-state to another is the desire for a better life than the previous or the present status. International migration can be a source of positivity and negativity to a nation-state as it depends on the way the particular nation state decides to handle the subject matter, this is where the efficiency of the national commission for refugees, migrants and internally displaced persons. International migration is naturally complex. It can affect a nation state politically, culturally and socioeconomically by taking out strength from the labor force of a country. In other words, international migration brings decline in socioeconomic development. The present paper is on the concept of international migration; the age of migration and implications for destination.

Introduction

International migration is the movement of people across international borders for the purpose of settlement. International migrants change their usual place of residence from one country to another. The United Nations suggests that the degree of permanence of the migration should be measured over a 12-month period, so that shorter stays in another country are not classified as permanent international migration. When passengers arrive in a country, they are asked whether they intend to stay for less than 3 months, classifying them as visitors; for between 3 months and 12 months, classifying them as short-term migrants; or for 12 months or more, classifying them as long-term migrants. This is a prospective measurement of migration. Alternatively, people can be surveyed at their current place of residence and asked where they were living 12 months ago. If the answer is another country, then they are classified as international migrants. This is a retrospective measurement of migration. It is also possible to measure international migration by asking migrants leaving a country to register their departure and to ask a question about migration of those new registering in countries which maintain a comprehensive population register. All measurements of international migration are fraught with error and disagreement. Those expressing an intention to stay for more than 12 months may return home before the year has ended, while visitors may decide to apply for permanent

residence after arrival. Short-term migrants may become long term and vice versa. People leaving a country frequently fail to register their departures, and in many cases they are not departing from one permanent residence but moving between one residence and another on a seasonal or periodic basis. Poulain and colleagues have documented the statistical systems used to record international migration between European states, and present a matrix of migration flows between EU member states, from both receiving and sending country statistics. Most cells have at least one entry, though there are a few empty cells. The discrepancies between the two views can be very large: in 2002 Germany reported 78 739 people migrating to Poland, while Poland reported only 2335 arriving! In general, immigration statistics are considered more trustworthy as immigrants normally have to fill in a form on entry or to obtain work, education, or healthcare. To arrive at a reasonable estimate of the migration flows between European countries, Raymer had to design an ingenious and elaborate algorithm to make best use of the available data. There is also error introduced as a result of failure to count illegal migrants. Flows within Europe, though large, are not the largest international migrations in Europe, which involve migrations from and to the world outside Europe. In recent years, both Spain and Italy have received very large flows of migrants from abroad, 2004 of 610 000 and 558 000 net migrants, respectively, compared with 204 000 into the United Kingdom, 105 000 into France, and only 82 000 into Germany, according to statistics assembled by the Vienna Institute of Demography. A team led by Kupiszewski at the Central European Forum for Migration and Population Research has recently carried out explorations of the future population of 27 European countries under different international migration scenarios. They show that under no plausible scenario of net gains from international migration will there be much alleviation of the effects of population aging on old-age dependency. The projection model interestingly divides the international migration flows into two sets, those between the 27 countries which are modeled as part of a multistate population projection, and the net immigration flows from outside Europe which will make the biggest impact on the future population. In effect, what was formerly international migration within Europe has become very similar to domestic or international migration.

Meaning of International Migration

According to Iheanacho and Ughaerumba (2015), migration can be traced to the existence of the first set of humans on earth. Migration has taken various patterns such as slave trade, colonization, urbanization, industrialization and globalization. Movement of persons (migrants) from one place to another has been traced from the precolonial era (precisely slave trade era) to colonial era. Although the nation-state was recognized as Nigeria as at then as it had a kingdom and empire structure. This made it difficult to be described as internal or international structure. The most important is to note that migration in Africa (Nigeria) can be traced to this era. During these eras' migration was both forced and voluntary. In Nigeria, during the 1960s international migration became the new trend and was at its increase as Nigerians and other Africans left their respective states for Europe while the south-south pathways of migration also existed, as Africans migrated to various parts of West African neighboring states mostly for trade purpose (regional Integration). According to Fayomi

(2016), international migration is mostly influenced by economic reasons which can be for employment, trade purposes, high favorable standard of living and fair-weather conditions for agriculture among other reasons. Tacoli and Okali (2017) also explained international migration to be a feature of globalization as the world is interconnected and interdependent on each other. This reveals that International migration is the movement across international borders or nation-states. The literature went further in confirming the statement earlier made that international migration can positively contribute to sustainable development of nations states. International migration is the movement of individuals from one international boundary to another. Individuals who move from one place to another are known as migrants. International migration involves two set of individuals these are the irregular migrants and regular migrants. Nonye (2016) also reveals that movement of individuals (migrants) from ne boundary to another has been on its increase. This international migration activity can be engaged nationally and regionally. International migration can be permanent or temporary. Nse (2018) validates the statement that international migration can trigger creativity, innovation, trade, entrepreneurship among others development. This subject matter (international migration) recently has become a topic for debates and discussions by nation states. Fredrick (2016) reveals international migration to be a process of moving across borders. International migration in Nigeria can be traced as far back as the pre-colonial era, precisely the slave trade era in which humans were seen as commodities to be traded and transported to Europe as slaves. The colonial era also experienced international migration as various ethnic groups and other Africans transported themselves from one place to another spreading the information and educating their fellow individuals on the ideology known as nationalism at that time and also moved from one place to another for trade purposes (Kerion, 2016) during this colonial and post-colonial period, a policy to sponsor Nigerians abroad was also introduced so as to build up leaders who will lead and develop the nation-state since the British (Europeans) opened the eyes of Africans to western education (Akinirinde and Olukoya, 2017) West (2018) reveals that Africa in which Nigeria belonged has the largest source of migrants . However, the economic and political instability of Nigeria, has many citizens to seek refuge and economic prosperity in other countries. For this study, international migrants the movement of citizens from Nigeria to other countries in search of employment, permanent residence, etc. international migration is seen as a reaction to the “pull” and “push” factors exposed to migrants, as they are expected to act as human beings first before acting up as migrants. International migration of individuals as earlier stated can be voluntary or involuntary. European Union (2017) reveals that the number of migrants grow continually as it is evidently seen this means that international migration will always be on its increase as its likely to be inevitable due to the interconnected nature of nation-state and the nature of the international system. Also, the various transportations for easy movement, as a result of the benefits of globalization makes individuals engage in international migration easily. Adetunji (2015) also reveals international migration to be the movement of individuals across national boundaries. One of the reasons behind the migrant’s movement from one nation-state to another is the desire for a better life than the previous or the present statues. International migration can be a source of positivity and negativity to a nation-state as it depends on the way the particular nation state

decides to handle the subject matter, this is where the efficiency of the national commission for refugees, migrants and internally displaced persons. According to Zoomer cited in Fayomi (2018), international migration is naturally complex. It can affect a nation state politically, culturally and socioeconomically by taking out strength from the labor force of a country. In other words, international migration brings decline in socioeconomic development.

Types of International Migration

Types and kinds of international migration changes over time, reasons are that researchers reveals new and various categories of international migration as they get interested on the subject matter. This reveals that international migration is a subject that keeps on emerging in various ways as the world and various nations states in the international system changes socio economically and geopolitically Terrence (2016) according to Jennissen (2016), there are various types and kind of international migration. These are:

- International labour migration
- Return international migration
- Chain international migration
- Asylum international migration

International labour migration:

This is majorly explained to be migration for the purpose of job opportunities, exchange of skill and expertise from one nation state to the other. This kind of international migration can also be influenced by nation state bilateral relations (Bean, 2006 cited in Sander et al 2016). It can also be a decision of the individual (migrants). All kinds of migrants (skilled, semi-skilled, unskilled) with the intention of migrating for jobs of any sort of venturing into labour migration. In addition, labour migration are engaged by individuals (migrants) seeking job opportunities in their various destination states (Jennissen, 2016). Labour international migration can also be engaged by voluntary migrants for the sole purpose of working or getting a comfortable job. This is mostly more of a personal gain and indirectly profitable to receiving states. Simply put, labour international migration is the transfer of skill from one nation state to another (Brady, 2017).

Return international migration:

takes place when a particular individual (migrant) retires back home to his/her nation state of origin after leaving the home nation state to another for quite some time or a long period of time. Sometimes, migrants go to their various destination nation states to make some amount of money after that retires back to start a business or permanently back to live after studies abroad. It can also be explained as the relocating of migrants back to their respective countries (Abraham, 2016).

Chain international migration

This is described as movements in which various individuals migrate out of their home countries with the sole aim of joining their family members abroad. This type of international migration can also be referred to as re-unification. This involves invitations from family members and friends in the destination's individuals wish to arrive at (Vincent, 2016).

Asylum international migration

This is practiced by asylum seekers (individuals) that seek refuge in a destination nation state due to frustration and push factors surrounding them in their home countries. They describe themselves as been in need of help and refuge. This is also described as forced international migration. This type of international migration is mostly engaged by refugees, internally displaced persons and others who claim refugee statues (Donald, 2017). According to Amewhule (2016), international migration is grouped into three (3) types. These are:

- Economic international migration
- Environmental international migration
- Political international migration

Economic International Migration

Economic International Migration is associated and engaged by job seekers and other economic related reasons. In this type of international migration, the migrant's sole purpose is to apply his/her skill for exchange of money. These migrants can also have intentions of improving his/her standard of living through better job opportunities in their destination countries (Joel, 2016).

Environmental international Migration

Environmental international Migration is influenced by push and pull factors such as desert nature in home nation state, rise in sea levels, drought among other factors while the pull

factors is perceived as multiple found opportunities in that region such as serene environment in the destination state among other factors (Mahmoud ,2017).

Political international migration

Political international migration is also influenced by political push factors in the home nation state; such factor can be civil wars, corruption of leaders, political discrimination, and tribalism to mention a few (Mahmoud, 2018).

Migration Analysis

While the statistical analysis of international migration relies on some data external to the census (arrival and departure data, residence permit data, etc.), census analysis is important in analyzing immigration outcomes. Questions on birthplace and duration of residence within a country allow the identification of the migrant population, and cross-tabulations with various social and economic variables allow an assessment of levels of migrant participation and well-being. A limitation of the census method, however, is that longitudinal analysis of individuals or families is not possible except in some cases by inference between censuses. The analysis of internal migration is highly dependent on census data in countries which do not have comprehensive systems of residence registration. A question on usual residence at a previous point in time (e.g., 1 or 5 years ago) allows the construction of matrices of movement between different areas of a country. The degree of mobility measured by this method is dependent on the spatial resolution used, with the most detailed scale (any household movement) resulting in the highest levels of measured mobility. A common use of this method is to assess economic well-being of different regions of a country in relation to population mobility, especially in relation to the educational and occupational characteristics of the migrant population. The residual method of migration analysis may be used in the absence of census data on movement into or out of an area. Age–sex characteristics of the population of an area are compared between censuses so that a survival rate is applied to age–sex cohort between census 1 and census 2 and the difference between the hypothesized number of survivors at census 2 is compared to the actual cohort at census 2; the differences are taken to represent the net migration of each cohort between censuses.

Transnationalism

Transnationalism, in the context of international migration, refers to the repeated movement of immigrants and their families between their homeland and their receiving country, and the ongoing set of contacts and activities that they sustain across national borders. It replaces the older idea of permanent settlement in a new land with the notion of temporary settlement and circular movement between origin and destination. This ‘transnationalism from below’ includes more than continuing social connections with families and friends. In addition to such social traffic there are also economic and political linkages. Remittances, funds returned to the homeland by overseas workers, now contribute significant levels of local economic development to homeland states. Diaspora politics also engage some immigrants, and just as diasporas participate in homeland politics, so some sending countries are reaching out to maintain connections with their overseas citizens and former citizens. Transnationalism presents some challenges for nation-states, for migrants, aided where it exists by dual citizenship, live in a social space that crosses national borders and may opportunistically make use of different resources in both sending and

receiving countries. This border-spanning behavior raises some important questions about the meaning of national belonging and citizenship in a globalizing transnational era.

Taylor, G.

Griffith Taylor was a prolific author of wide-ranging works on the influence of environmental controls in settlement expansion, international migration, racial evolution and dispersal, physical geography, meteorology, urban and regional geography, and Antarctic exploration. He played a key role in heated academic and public debates on the competing claims of 'environmentalism' and 'possibilism' during the first half of the twentieth century. Taylor is also recognized as an innovative promoter of geography's creative educational and civic role as an interdisciplinary science, for incorporating graphical presentations of biological and geological analogies in a lively pursuit of correlations between anthropological, historical, and other data, and for distinctive prescience in what would become central thrusts in geography's modern engagement in issues of resource appraisal, environmental management, and sustainable development.

The Age of Migration

Castles and Miller famously described the contemporary period as the 'age of migration'. Since the end of World War II, international migration has grown in volume and changed in character, they argue, in two main stages: 1945 to 1973 (the end of this first period was marked by the global oil crisis) and 1974 to the present. The first stage of global, international migration was characterized by the migration of workers from the European periphery to Western Europe (such as through the 'guest worker' systems described below); the migration of 'colonial workers' to their former colonial powers (such as the migration of Algerians to France and Jamaicans to Britain); and a pattern of permanent migration to North America and Australia from Europe (initially) and after the mid-1960s from Asia and Latin America. The second stage of post-war migration has been characterized, in contrast, by a decline of labor migration to Western Europe. This stage has also seen family reunification among former foreign and colonial workers (leading to the creation of new ethnic minority communities within particular cities); the continuation of economically motivated migration to immigration regions within North America and Australasia (but with a significant change in the source countries of these immigrants); mass movements of refugees and asylum seekers; and the international mobility of highly skilled migrants (both temporary and permanent). To this list should be added the significant recent increase in economic migration between European Union (EU) member states, as a consequence of recent EU expansion (such as the substantial migration from Poland to the UK).

Implications for Destination

In relation to the destinations, many argue that migrants are among the most entrepreneurial of groups and that most societies benefit from their presence. Most migrants are economically active and in many countries within Europe and elsewhere in the developed world where the population is aging and birth rates are well below replacement level, there is a growing recognition that migrant labor may be the only solution to the growing 'demographic deficit'. It is no surprise that so many countries actively encourage skilled immigrants to enter, but at the same time they actively discourage the entry of other groups with different backgrounds. Thus, despite the benefits that most migrants bring they are also threatening for some in the

destination societies. Migrant bodies are often depicted as diseased, racialized, criminalized, and undeserving. They may compete for jobs, one consequence of which is the depression of wage rates. Many complain that they make undue use of public services, especially healthcare. The impression of immigrants is therefore contradictory. While celebrating the diversity of ethnic difference in some aspects of daily life, such as the increasing breadth of cuisine available in most Western countries, fears of being under siege from groups who will resist being 'assimilated' are commonly portrayed in the media. The irony of this perspective in New World countries where the white majority are themselves descendents of immigrant groups is rarely acknowledged. Research on the geography of immigrant settlement contributes to the tendency among some to maintain a 'them' and 'us' perspective with its focus on segregation, ghettoization, and 'proximity to whites'. Whether ghettos ever existed remains a debated point and, in an increasingly mobile world, the ability of ethnic groups to retain a cohesive community without clustering geographically is becoming more recognized. More recent research, particularly in the US, which apparently links the flows of incoming international migrants into key 'port-of-entry' states and cities with the selective out-migration of lower class whites who find the competition for jobs and housing too difficult, helps to fuel such concerns. Referred to by some as a 'demographic balkanization', critics have argued that the link between these two broad migration processes is at best weak (the overlap between immigrant and native employment markets is not great in most places) and that the use of such terminology is particularly problematic and inflammatory suggesting, as it does, an immigrant-induced breakup of a unified nation.

Summary and Conclusion

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References

- Akanji, S. (2012) "The Drivers of Immigration in Contemporary Society: Unequal Distribution of Resources and Opportunities". *Human Ecology*. 35 (6): 775–776. doi: 10.1007/s10745-007-9111-z .
- Akanji, S. (2012) . "The Labor Demand Curve is Downward Sloping: Reexamining the Impact of Immigration on the Labor Market". *The Quarterly Journal of Economics* . 118 (4): 1335–1374.
- Akinirinde, G. and Olukoya, F. (2017). "*On the Corner: Day Labor in Africa*". UCLA Center for the Study of Urban Poverty. Archived from the original (PDF) on 10 October 2017. Retrieved 11 December 2017.
- Anarfi, T. & Piel, R. (2015). "Welfare effects of illegal immigration" (PDF). *Journal of Population Economics* . 22 (1): 131–144. doi : 10.1007/s00148-007-0182-3 .
- Asiedu, M., Anarfi et al, Twum-BaahManuh et al (2016). "Learning to Be Illegal: Undocumented Youth and Shifting Legal Contexts in the Transition " (PDF).
- Awumbbila et al (2017). "Understanding the effects of legalising undocumented immigrants". *Vox EU.org* . Archived from the original on 17 May 2018. Retrieved 16 May 2018.
- Crimes by Illegals are Buried in Amnesty Push" . Archived from the original on 14 July 2014. Retrieved 4 June 2014.
- Derek, F. (2016). "The Unwelcome Return of 'Illegals'. *The New York Times*.

- Die, M.; Asiedu, F. (2016). "Are undocumented immigrants committing a crime? Not necessarily". Archived from the original on 4 July 2018. Retrieved 11 July 2018.
- Dietrich, F. (2015) "*Here's the Reality About Illegal Immigrants in the United States*". Archived from the original on 29 June 2018. Retrieved 18 July 2018.
- Dietrich, G. (2015). *121 murders attributed to illegals released by Obama administration*". The Washington Times. Archived from the original on 11 August 2015. Retrieved 21 August 2015.
- Donald, M. (2017). User Generated Racism: Russia's media and migrants". *The European Journalism Observatory*. Archived from the original on 5 May 2014. Retrieved 5 May 2018.
- Done, Y. (2017). *Asylum seekers', 'illegal immigrants' and entry without a visa*". Advisory Guidelines 2011. Australian Press Council. Archived from the original on 1 August 2015. Retrieved 5 May 2014.
- Fayomi, D. (2016). The Economic Contribution of Unauthorized Workers: An Industry Analysis". *Regional Science and Urban Economics* . 67: 119–134.
- Federal Reserve Bank of Atlanta, Does Employing Undocumented Workers Give Firms a Competitive Advantage? , November 2012" (PDF). Archived (PDF) from the original on 12 April 2013. Retrieved 8 November 2012.
- Fredrick, L. (2016). "*The Economic Effect of Immigration Policies: Analyzing and Simulating the U.S. Case*" (PDF).
- Hiltner, D. & Stephen, T. (2017). "*Illegal, Undocumented, Unauthorized: The Terms of Immigration Reporting*". The New York Times.
- Iheanacho, F. and Ughaerumba, R. (2015). *Beyond Smoke and Mirrors: Mexican Immigration in an Era of Economic Integration*. Yussell Sage Foundation.
- Isaac, D. (2016). "The labor market effects of reducing the number of illegal immigrants". *Review of Economic Dynamics*. 18 (4): 792– 821. doi : 10.1016/j.red.2015.07.005 .
- Jacklyn, G. (2016). *Missing the Boat?* A paper delivered to 'Reporting on Asylum Seekers and Refugees: A Walkley Media Forum' convened by the Media Entertainment & Arts Alliance, 19 June 2017" (PDF). Proceedings Reporting on Asylum Seekers and Refugees: A Walkley Media Forum, Regatta Hotel, Brisbane, Australia. Queensland University of Technology. Archived (PDF) from the original on 5 May 2014. Retrieved 5 May 2014. Illegals". 13 December 2011.
- Jennisen, H. (2016). *You Say 'Illegal Alien.' I Say 'Undocumented Immigrant.' Who's Right?'*. 18 December 2017.

- Jennissen, H. (2016) "Drop the I-Word Campaign". Race Forward. 23 September 2013. Archived from the original on 23 February 2014. Retrieved 2 March 2014.
- Joel, P. (2016). "How journalism can rid migration of its sour reputation". *European Journalism Centre*. Archived from the original on 5 May 2014. Retrieved 5 May 2014.
- Jones, G. (2016) "The State of U.S. Immigration Policy: The Quandary of Economic Methodology and the Relevance of Economic Research to Know". *Journal of Law, Economics and Policy*. 5 (1): 177–193. Archived from the original on 21 December 2009. Retrieved 10 December, 2009.
- Kerion, M. (2016). *Economic Effects of Granting Legal Status and Citizenship to Undocumented Immigrants*. Pew Hispanic Center. Archived (PDF) from the original on 11 December 2016. Retrieved 11 December 2017.
- Tacol, H.I and Okali, C. (2017). "Survey of Migrants, Part One: Attitudes about Immigration and Major Demographic Characteristics". *Journal of Economic Dynamics and Control*. 34 (12): 2547–2567.
- Tacoli, H. and Okali, C. (2017). "The Impact of Unauthorized Immigrants on the Budgets of State and Local Governments". 6 December 2017. Archived from the original on 22 July 2016. Retrieved 28 June 2017.
- Terrence, S. (2016) "Key Migration Terms". 14 January 2015. Archived from the original on 12 January 2018. Retrieved 11 January 2018.
- West, Z. (2018) " "Illegal Alien" Is One of Many Correct Legal Terms for "Illegal Immigrant". Cato Institute. 14 October 2019. Retrieved 15 October 2019. Words Matter PICUM". Archived from the original on 20 December 2017. Retrieved 11 January 2018.
- Zoomer et al cited in Fayomi, S. (2018). *"Trade, Legal, and Illegal Immigration"* (PDF). University of Westminster. Archived from the original (PDF) on 17 February 2017. Retrieved 12 December 2018.[dubious – discuss] Accessed 11 December 2018.